

Table 2. Reaction pattern of 15 rice varieties to 3 *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates in Egypt.

Variety	Reaction to isolate			Mean	Reaction	
	Po 361 ^a	Po 359	Po GMI		Egypt	Phil/India
<i>Indica</i>						
Cauvery	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.3	R	S
Ratna	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	S
IR50	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	S
IR36	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	MR
IR28	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	MS
Giza 181	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	S
Rasi	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	R
<i>Japonica</i>						
Gz 159	8.0	9.0	9.0	8.6	S	S
Gz 171	6.5	9.0	9.0	8.2	S	S
Gz 172	8.0	9.0	9.0	8.6	S	S
Reiho	7.5	9.0	9.0	8.5	S	S
Shin 2	5.5	6.5	6.0	6.0	MS	S
Aichi Asahi	8.0	9.0	9.0	8.6	S	S
Kanto 51	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.3	R	S
Toride 1	1.0	1.5	1.0	1.1	R	R
Mean	3.5	4.1	4.0			
CV (1)	7.1			Subplot LSD (0.05) = .27		
CV (2)	6.0			(Varieties) (0.01) = .36		
LSD Main plot at 0.05						
Isolates at 0.01						
Interaction LSD at	0.05	= 0.47				
	0.01	= 0.64				

^aAverage value of 2 replications. Po 361 from Kafr El-Sheikh governorate, Po 359 from Dakhalia governorate. Po GMI from Gharbia governorate

others that have shown more durable resistance in other rice-growing environ-

ments appear to be better donors of B1 resistance in Egypt. ■

Changes in rice leaf pigment due to tungro (RTV) infection

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Chlorosis and orange yellow color in leaves are characteristic symptoms of RTV disease in rice. We investigated the effect of RTV infection on green pigment (chlorophyll), orange pigment (carotene), and yellow pigment (xanthophyll) at different stages of pathogenesis.

Fifteen-day-old seedlings of susceptible TN1 were inoculated with RTV by

releasing three viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* (Dist.) per seedling. Infected leaves were graded as 1/3 orange yellow, 2/3 orange yellow, or completely orange yellow. Chlorophyll content was extracted and estimated in 80% acetone. Carotene and xanthophyll were extracted with 95% ethanol and 85% methanol, respectively, and estimated colorimetrically.

Chlorophyll content of diseased leaves was reduced in proportion to the length of orange-yellow color on a leaf (see table). In leaves that had turned completely orange yellow, chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll were reduced by 90, 94, and 91%, respectively.

Effect of RTV on pigment of rice leaves. Coimbatore, India.

Leaf color	Chlorophyll a	Chlorophyll b	Total chlorophyll	Carotene	Xanthophyll
Completely orange yellow	0.234	0.078	0.312	ND*	ND
2/3 orange yellow	0.564	0.119	0.689	0.005	0.003
1/3 orange yellow	1.380	0.680	2.184	ND	ND
Healthy	2.300	1.370	3.672	0.003	0.002
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.26	0.110	0.190		

^a ND = not determined

A slight increase in carotene and xanthophyll content was found in diseased leaves. ■

Development of kresek symptoms on some rice varieties

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Xanthomonas campestris pv. *oryzae* (Xco) can cause kresek symptoms on rice seedlings. Great variations have been found among strains of Xco in terms of their pathogenicity in the rice plant.

We induced kresek in the screenhouse using different strains of Xco on seven rice varieties. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with two replications, with rice varieties Pelita 1-1, Java 14, Gemar, Cisadane, Citanduy, TNI, and IR54 in the main plots and three isolates or strains of Xco in the subplots.

Roots of 21-d-old seedlings were washed, dip-inoculated for 15 min with 48-h-old bacterial suspension ($\pm 10^9$ cfu/ml), and seedlings transplanted in a wooden seedling box. Disease incidence was recorded 14 d after inoculation.

Symptom development varied (see table). Cisadane had the least disease symptoms with all three Xco strains, followed by Java 14, Pelita 1-1, and Gemar. Mean infection ranged from 9.7 to 44.3%. ■

Development of kresek symptoms on 7 rice varieties Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988.

Variety	Wilted plant ^a (%)			
	Si 8502	Si 8401	Si 8519	Mean
Gemar	16.55	12.68	17.83	15.67 ab
Cisadane	9.26	11.93	7.97	9.72 a
Citanduy	26.75	21.65	20.72	23.04 bc
Pelita 1-1	14.56	19.94	11.95	15.48 ab
IR54	36.99	33.85	22.62	31.15 c
Java 14	14.31	16.06	16.05	15.47 ab
TNI	51.09	48.74	32.94	44.26 d
Mean	24.21 a	23.55 a	18.58 b	-
CV variety (%)	= 33.28			
CV isolates (%)	= 17.73			

^a Isolates Si 8502, Si 8401, and Si 8519 represented Indonesia bacterium groups III, V, and VI, respectively. Means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly by DMRT (P = 0.05).